

ESiWACE3 Newsletter

Issue #9 / August 2025

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News

2nd Call for Proposals: ESIWACE3 Support on Domain-Specific Tools and Technologies

The ESIWACE3 Consortium is pleased to announce the second open call for proposals under Support on Domain-Specific Tools and Technologies.

This service offers in-kind support to developers of Earth System Models (ESMs), helping them adopt and integrate tools developed within the ESIWACE3 ecosystem. The objective is to improve model efficiency and prepare ESM software for current and emerging (pre-)exascale computing platforms.

The selected projects will receive tailored technical guidance and engineering effort from ESIWACE3 experts.

[What Kind of Support is Offered?](#)

This call supports the adoption of specialized tools that address common performance and portability challenges in ESM development, including:

- **Mixed-Precision Tools:**
Use AutoRPE (CPU) or Kernel Tuner (GPU) to explore precision reduction for improved throughput and energy efficiency.
- **Cross-Platform Deployment:**
Receive help with Spack/EasyBuild and software engineering best practices to improve portability across diverse HPC platforms.
- **Automatic Performance Profiling:**
Integrate the APP tool to automatically generate detailed performance reports for weather and climate models.
- **Containerisation for ESMs:**
Package models and tools into containers to improve reproducibility and simplify deployment on EuroHPC and other systems.

Due to the limited timeframe and scope of the service, the scientific validation of model changes will remain the responsibility of the applicant.

Who Can Apply?

The call is open to all groups developing and maintaining ESM components, including teams outside the ESiWACE3 consortium.

Priority is given to proposals that aim to:

- Improve the main development branch of a well-established model or component,
- Follow sustainable and reusable software engineering practices,
- Be developed as open-source with a permissive license.

Timeline

- Call Opens: 1 June 2025
- Deadline: Open until the end of the project or until all available Person-Months are allocated.

Proposals will be reviewed on a rolling basis.

Proposal Review Process

Each submission will be evaluated in two stages:

1. Technical Feasibility – reviewed by the relevant ESiWACE3 service providers.
2. Scientific Impact – assessed by an external review panel.

Selected projects will receive an in-kind contribution from the consortium in the form of expert support, guidance, and implementation effort.

How to Apply

For full details on the tools, eligibility, and application process, download the official Call for Proposals PDF [here](#)

Proposals can be submitted via our [online application form](#).

Advance your ESM code with cutting-edge tools and expert support from ESiWACE3 – apply now!

Call for Proposals

Support on domain specific tools and technologies

This call for proposals aims at **supporting the ESM-developing communities** in the **adoption of tools**, developed in the landscape of ESIWACE3, to help them **improve the model efficiency** and **readying the software** to enable model execution **on existing and near-future (pre-)exascale computing platforms.**

Mixed precision: Kernel Tuner & AutoRPE

With these tools, we can help anyone who wants to optimize their compute-heavy, CPU and GPU-accelerated codes

 AutoRPE

Cross-platform deployment: Spack and good practices

This service will help developers to write and test on different environment the Spack/Easybuild recipe for their application.

 easybuild

Automatic profiling: APP

This service supports applicants in integrating and configuring the APP tool within their models, and in understanding its reports.

Containerisation for ESMs

Successful applicants will receive support in containerising existing climate model codes and analysis tools.

ESIWACE3 Contributes to New White Paper on Best Practices for European Centres of Excellence

We are proud to announce that ESIWACE3 has contributed to a newly published white paper titled “Guidance and Best Practices for European Centres of Excellence (CoEs)”, now available on [Zenodo](#).

This comprehensive document brings together practical frameworks, lessons learned, and actionable recommendations for strengthening the sustainability, innovation potential, and societal impact of Centres of Excellence across Europe. It is aimed at a wide audience, including project coordinators, innovation managers, policymakers, and business developers involved in EU-funded research and innovation.

As a contributing CoE, ESIWACE3 shared its experience and methodologies in managing complex HPC infrastructures, fostering cross-sector collaboration, and building pathways for long-term sustainability. The guidance includes insights into tools such as the Business Model Canvas, strategies for ecosystem development, and reproducible approaches to commercialization—many of which have been informed by our work and lessons learned throughout the ESIWACE project series.

We encourage our community to explore the white paper and consider how its findings can support the continued evolution of high-impact research centres in Europe.

 Read the full publication here:

<https://zenodo.org/records/15862001>

ESiWACE3 on Supercomputing in Europe Podcast

We are pleased to announce the release of a new episode of the Supercomputing in Europe podcast, featuring Mario Acosta, Principal Investigator of the ESIWACE3 Centre of Excellence.

In this episode, Mario discusses how high-performance computing (HPC) is driving innovation in weather, climate, and the energy transition. The conversation explores ESIWACE3's role in advancing Earth system modeling at exascale and its collaborations with key initiatives such as HANAMI and Destination Earth.

The episode also highlights the work of EoCoE (Energy-oriented Centre of Excellence), showcasing how HPC-based numerical simulation supports the shift toward low-carbon energy solutions.

Podcast Highlights:

- The mission and vision of ESIWACE3 in the European HPC landscape
- How supercomputing empowers climate and energy research
- Synergies with projects like HANAMI and Destination Earth
- Real-world applications of simulation excellence in sustainability

 Listen now on your favorite platform:

 [Spotify](#)

 [Apple Podcasts](#)

**SUPERCOMPUTING IN
EUROPE**

*Interview and editing by Maria Arista Romero
Audio mixing by Apostolos Vasileiadis*

This episode was made possible thanks to the support of EuroHPC and CASTIEL2.

Stay tuned for more stories on how HPC is shaping the future of science and society across Europe.

Events

External events

External events in which ESIWACE3 has participated since the last issue of the ESIWACE Newsletter:

- [National Hydrological and Climate Modeling Seminar, Helsinki \(Finland\), 20 November 2024.](#) [Talk](#)
- [Hidalgo2 - Hackathon on Atmosphere-Fire interaction, Madrid \(Spain\), 2 December 2024.](#) [Talk](#)
- [ChEEsE Workshop, Online, 10 December 2024.](#) [Talk](#)
- [HiPEAC Conference, 20-22 February 2024.](#) Round table. Organization. Booth

Updates

Deliverables:

Deliverable 3.1 Report on data layout concepts for Earth system model data

This Deliverable D3.1, reports about data layouts concepts for large-scale datasets of Earth System Models (ESMs), with a focus on the ICON model setting scalability and efficiency as priorities. Data formats and storage layouts like GRIB/fdb have shown limitations in handling large files containing global fields and providing precise data access due to the inevitable increase of data volumes and its continuous growth.

Read D3.1 [here](#).

Deliverable 5.4 Report on Training Materials

This deliverable presents the training material developed during ESIWACE3, including both general HPC content for early career scientists and specialized content from project work packages, reviewed for pedagogical quality and compiled in an online repository for broad community access.

Read D5.4 [here](#).

Milestones:

Milestone 1.3 Containerized version of EC-Earth4 running on one EuroHPC platform

Milestone regarding the publishing of short information about the use case coreved and container and platform specs.

Read M1.3 [here](#).

Milestone 3.4 Prototype of the data layout concepts developed and demonstrated in a first implementation

Report on milestone M3.4 on the prototypical implementation and evaluation of data storage and layout methods.

Read M3.4 [here](#).

Milestone 4.4 Service assessment 2

This milestone reports on the first fully completed service projects delivered by ESIWACE3, introduces updated terminology for service types to enhance clarity and visibility, and summarizes the outcomes of the four service calls held so far under the new naming scheme.

Read M4.4 [here](#).

News from the neighbours

Training events

Find collected information on upcoming and past training events from all consortium partners and projects we are involved with [here](#).